

Hippuric Acid—A Better Reagent for Quantitative Estimation of Zirconium

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Hippuric acid has been found to be a better suited reagent for gravimetric estimation of zirconium. Even microquantity i.e., 1–2 mg. of zirconium can be estimated accurately in pH range 4–5.2. Because of variable composition the precipitate is ignited and zirconium is weighed as ZrO_2 , Ba^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Fe^{3+} are removed by single precipitation. Ti^{4+} , UO_2^{2+} , Al^{3+} and trivalent cerite earth ions are removed by double precipitation. Zn^{2+} , Be^{2+} , Ce^{3+} , $V_2O_4^{2+}$ ions interfere.

SHASTRI and Raghava Rao¹ used phenoxy-acetic acid for gravimetric determination of zirconium. Later various reagents were suggested for quantitative determination of zirconium by different workers^{2–8}. Very little work appears to have been carried out on analytical aspects of hippuric acid. Author⁹ has used this reagent for gravimetric estimation of thorium and in the present communication its use for quantitative estimation of zirconium has been discussed.

As a result of systematic investigation of hippuric acid as a selective reagent for zirconium estimation, it has been observed that this reagent gives a white crystalline, insoluble and easily washable precipitate. This reagent is better suited as even microquantity i.e. 1–2 mg. of zirconium can be estimated accurately. The precipitate is quantitative in presence of electrolyte (e.g. NH_4NO_3) between pH 4.0–5.2 maintained with the addition of sodium acetate and acetic acid buffer solution. At higher and lower pH poor results are obtained. In presence of H_2SO_4 the estimation of zirconium is not possible. The composition of precipitate varies and therefore can not be weighed as such. However this difficulty is overcome by weighing as oxide after igniting the precipitate.

The metal ions e.g., Ba^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Fe^{3+} do not give precipitate with this reagent and are thus removed from zirconium by single precipitation. For separation from Ti^{4+} , UO_2^{2+} , Al^{3+} and trivalent cerite earths double precipitation is required. The estimation is not possible in presence of Zn^{2+} , Be^{2+} , Ce^{3+} , $V_2O_4^{2+}$ because of hydrolysis presence of zirconium.

Experimental

Reagent Solution :

A 2% solution was prepared by dissolving the requisite quantity of K-salt of hippuric acid in distilled water.

Standard Zirconium Solution :

Solution of zirconium was prepared from requisite amount of Merck's G.R. grade oxychloride of metal in definite amount of distilled water.

Solution of other cations :

Metal salts, mostly chloride and nitrates, employed in preparation of solution of inorganic ions were of B.D.H. A.R. Grade.

Analytical Procedure

To the boiling zirconium solution containing varying amounts of zirconium salts, in presence of ammonium nitrate (approximately 5 mg/100 ml.), a hot 2% solution of K-salt of hippuric acid was added with constant stirring in slight excess. The pH of the solution was adjusted at 4.63. The precipitate was kept on water bath for fifteen minutes and was allowed to settle down. It was then filtered through a Whatman filter paper No. 42, washed with 0.1% reagent solution. The precipitate was ignited and weighed as ZrO_2 . The result of estimation are listed in Table 1.

Separation from Foreign Ions :

Zirconium may easily be separated from Ba^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Fe^{3+} by single precipitation, whereas Ti^{4+} , UO_2^{2+} , Al^{3+} and trivalent cerite earth ions are removed by double precipitation. Zn^{2+} , Be^{2+} , Ce^{3+} and $V_2O_4^{2+}$ ions interfere. The experimental results are recorded in Table 2.

Effect of pH :

The effect of hydrogen ion concentration on precipitation of zirconium was studied in range of 3.42–5.89 pH values and the results are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF VARYING AMOUNTS OF ZIRCONIUM USING HIPPURIC ACID AT pH 4.63

Expt. No.	ZrO ₂ taken g	ZrO ₂ found g	Error g
1.	0.1212	0.1214	+ .0002
2.	0.0968	0.0968	± .0000
3.	0.0728	0.0728	± .0000
4.	0.0485	0.0486	+ .0001
5.	0.0243	0.0244	+ .0001
6.	0.0125	0.0125	± .0000
7.	0.0073	0.0072	- .0001
8.	0.0040	0.0040	± .0000
9.	0.0030	0.0031	+ .0001
10.	0.0010	0.0010	± .0010

TABLE 3—ESTIMATION, OF ZIRCONIUM AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES, ZrO₂ TAKEN = 0.0456 g.

Expt. No.	pH of the solution	ZrO ₂ found g	Error g
1.	3.42	.0454	- .0002
2.	3.72	.0454	- .0002
3.	4.05	.0455	- .0001
4.	4.27	.0456	± .0000
5.	4.45	.0456	± .0000
6.	4.63	.0456	± .0000
7.	4.80	.0457	+ .0001
8.	4.99	.0456	± .0000
9.	5.23	.0457	+ .0001
10.	5.37	.0458	+ .0002
11.	5.57	.0458	+ .0002
12.	5.89	.0460	+ .0004

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF ZIRCONIUM FROM FOREIGN IONS ZrO₂ TAKEN = 0.0486 g. pH = 4.63

Expt. No.	Metal Ions		ZrO ₂ found g	Error g
	Added	g		
1.	Ba ²⁺	.1050	.04887	+ .0001
2.	Ca ²⁺	.0805	.0486	± .0000
3.	Sr ²⁺	.0448	.0486	± .0000
4.	Fe ³⁺	.2494	.0487	+ .0001
5.	Pb ²⁺	.0856	.0486	± .0000
6.	Zn ²⁺	Hydrolyses and cannot be separated		
7.	Be ²⁺	Hydrolyses and cannot be separated		
8.	Zn ²⁺ with 0.3N HCl	.1388	.0484	- .0002
9.	Al ³⁺	.0168	.0489	+ .0003
10.	Ce ³⁺	Hydrolyses and cannot be separated		
11.	Tl ⁴⁺	.1650	.0488	+ .0002
12.	Co ²⁺	.0524	.0486	± .0000
13.	Ni ²⁺	.1820	.0485	- .0001
14.	Mg ²⁺	.0264	.0486	+ .0000
15.	UO ₂ ²⁺	.1050	.0488	+ .0002
16.	V ₂ O ₄ ²⁺	Hydrolyses and cannot be separated		

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